

**HISTORY OF REPAIR AND REPAIR OF OLD MONUMENTS IN
KASHKADARYA REGION**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14777986>

Abstract: The article covers the history of the restoration and renovation of ancient historical and architectural monuments in the Kashkadarya region. It discusses the process of preserving and updating ancient monuments located in the region, including mosques, madrasas, mausoleums and other architectural structures. The article provides detailed information on the restoration of monuments in Shahrisabz, Karshi, Termez and other cities and districts, their significance and the work carried out to preserve the historical heritage. It also analyzes the role of archaeological and architectural research in the restoration of monuments in Kashkadarya, as well as large-scale programs and activities implemented to preserve historical monuments in the region. This article aims to document efforts to update the rich cultural heritage of the region and preserve it for future generations.

Key words and concepts: Karshi city, ancient, mosque, monument, mausoleum, national value, cultural heritage, historical object, repair, restoration, strengthening.

Recent trends in the global economy, such as the rapid development of tourism and recreation, have a significant impact on the Central Asian region, including Uzbekistan, in various regions and countries[1.1]. The visit to the places of pilgrimage is connected with the tourism sector, which in the 21st century became the most advantageous sphere in the world. Now he is in third place after the field of automotive and oil refining. The development of the tourism sector is important in strengthening the national and regional economy[2.1].

Since the first days of Uzbekistan's independence, respect for our history, culture, customs and traditions has grown even stronger. In particular, the legacy of many great scholars and saints who lived in our country in the past, as well as the scientific study, repair and restoration of historical and architectural monuments and structures built in our country thousands of years ago, are being carried out on a large scale.

Today, historical and architectural structures, mosques, madrasas, shrines, caravanserais and minarets located on the territory of Uzbekistan have been preserved. In particular, there are more than 8,200 cultural heritage sites in our country, 209 of which are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List of four museum cities - Ichan Kala in Khiva, the historical centers of Bukhara and Shakhrisabz, as well as ancient monuments located on the territory of Samarkand. [3.173]

Currently, 1,468 cultural heritage sites are preserved in the Kashkadarya region. Unfortunately, most of these monuments, which are masterpieces of the past, were not sufficiently protected during the former Soviet regime and could not retain their original appearance due to the lack of timely repair and strengthening work. It was during this period that most of the archaeological monuments not only in the oasis areas, but also in our republic, were destroyed.

According to the Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there were about 30,000 archaeological sites in our country until the 1960s. However, as a result of destruction, erosion, and incorporation into cultivated land, their number decreased to 9,000 in the late 1980s, and to 5,391 in the mid-1990s [4.6].

After our country gained independence, as in many other areas, fundamental reforms were carried out in the field of preservation and protection of cultural heritage objects. First of all, Article 49 of our Basic Law - the Constitution defines the issue of protection of ancient and historical monuments and monuments as follows: "Citizens are obliged to preserve and protect the historical, spiritual, cultural, scientific and natural heritage of the people of Uzbekistan. Historical, spiritual, cultural, scientific and natural heritage is protected by the state" [5, 24].

Since the first days of independence, a number of laws and resolutions have been adopted on the preservation and protection of cultural heritage monuments located on the territory of our republic. One of such documents is the relevant decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 9, 1992, and on April 27, 1992, Resolution No. 207 of the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to improve the activities of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and further improve its organizational system" came into force [6].

The repair and restoration of historical and architectural monuments in the Kashkadarya region was carried out in connection with the celebration of the anniversaries of the historical cities of the region and the birth dates of great

personalities, thinkers, sheikhs and pirs who lived in the oasis. In particular, since the fall of 2004, in connection with the celebration of the 2700th anniversary of the ancient city of Karshi, several historical structures that were built in the territory of this ancient city and have survived to this day have been restored, repaired and strengthened.

In the territory of the city of Karshi, one of the most ancient cities of southern Uzbekistan, several old mosques have survived to this day, one of which is the Kokgumbaz mosque. This monument was built by the Khan of Bukhara, Abdullakhan II (1557-1598), and the history of the construction of the structure was recorded in his works by the archaeologist M.YE. Masson as dating back to 999 AH (1590-1591 AD). The prayer hall served as a mosque for the residents of the city of Karshi and surrounding villages, and public gatherings were also organized in this place on holidays.

Due to the lack of attention paid to this monument with a long history for many years, it fell into a very deplorable state in the 80s-90s of the last 20th century. Although partial repairs were carried out on the monument in 1957, 1971, and 1975, these operations consisted only of strengthening and were carried out by unskilled craftsmen.

In their article "When it becomes a sacred place", journalist S. Boymurodova and museologist S. Pulatov noted the following about the condition of the Kokgumbaz mosque in the 90s of the 20th century: "Currently, 80% of architectural monuments in our region are in need of repair. The porches of the Kashkadarya bridge are sinking. Also, the back of the Kokgumbaz mosque in the city of Karshi, dating back to the 16th century, is cracked and water is leaking into it" [4].

This ancient monument found its true value during the years of independence. In 1996, in connection with the celebration of the 660th anniversary of the great commander Amir Temur, large-scale repair and restoration work was carried out on the Kokgumbaz Mosque, along with many other historical and architectural monuments in the city of Karshi.

This ancient structure has undergone a series of renovation works by experienced architects from the "Me'mor-96" repair workshop in Samarkand region, and traditional Muslim bricks produced by "Meros" LLC in Shahrisabz were widely used in the practices of strengthening the building and preserving its historical appearance. In connection with the 2700th anniversary of the city of Karshi, large-scale renovation and strengthening works were carried out in

the Kokgumbaz mosque in 2005-2006, and the historical structure was restored to its ancient appearance today [7, 146].

Another monument that was restored and renovated in 2004-2005 is the Odina Mosque and the ancient cistern located near it in the territory of the Karshi Registan. This monument is considered one of the largest architectural structures included in the Karshi Registan complex, and important historical information about its appearance, dimensions and other noteworthy aspects has been preserved. The prayer spaces inside the mosque are wide and high, topped with small domes, and thickly stacked brick columns are connected to each other through arcades. Seven steps lead up from the Registan Square to the square in front of the structure.

The famous literary scholar P. Ravshanov noted the following about the history of the construction of the Odina Mosque in his book History of Karshi: In 1385-1386, the great Amir Temur wintered in Karshi and built a large mosque in its center [8, 500]. Academician B. Ahmedov, in his historical novel "Amir Temur", wrote the following about the construction of the Odina Mosque: "When he heard from his beloved wife Bibikhanim that she had decided to build a grand mosque between the market and the caravanserai in the city of Karshi, Amir Temur's face was filled with pride and honor, approving this good initiative of his wife" [9, 361-362].

In 1938, this holy place was converted into a prison by a special decree of the former Soviet government, which could accommodate 150 convicts per year. A little later, in 1939, by a government decree, it was transformed into "Pre-trial Detention Center No. 5 of the Department of Execution of Sentences." Although this decree stipulated that 150 convicts would be accepted, in practice, from 600 to 800 convicts could be accommodated here per year and served their sentences [10].

Thanks to independence, attention to historical and architectural monuments and masterpieces of cultural heritage in our country has been radically renewed. Large-scale repair and restoration work has been carried out on these ancient objects. In particular, extensive creative work was carried out on the Odina Mosque under the auspices of the International Organization UNESCO and on the basis of the Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Preparations for the Celebration of the 2700th Anniversary of the City of Karshi" dated September 29, 2004 and the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Additional Measures for the

Celebration of the 2700th Anniversary of the City of Karshi” dated July 26, 2005 [11].

The prison on the territory of the Odina Mosque was relocated in late 2004, and in a short time the original architectural appearance of the monument was restored, and the surrounding area was completely landscaped. To the south of the Karshi Registan Square, an ancient cistern built by Abdullakhan II in the 16th century was also restored.

In accordance with the recommendations of the Head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the event held on August 31, 2021 on the occasion of the "Martyrs' Memory Day", the "Memory of Victims of Repression" Museum in the Karshi Du, which was operating in the Abu Ubayda ibn al-Jarrah complex, was moved to the Odina complex. Today, the Scientific Council and Scientific Seminar for Granting Degrees in Historical Sciences, established under the auspices of Karshi State University, continue their activities in this historical monument.

In conclusion, it can be noted that today the role of historical and architectural monuments and holy places in educating the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and creativity is incomparable. Considering the great importance of historical and cultural heritage sites in creating the foundation of the third Renaissance in new Uzbekistan, in developing the field of pilgrimage tourism in our country, it is no exaggeration to say that their preservation, restoration, strengthening, repair and passing on to future generations in their original state have today risen to the level of state policy.

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